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**Development of In-silico Strategies
To Advance the 3Rs in Toxicity Test-
ing**

Erasmus+ Curricular Internship Report
BSc in Bioinformatics

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July 2021

Para a Inês, por tudo

To Inês, for everything

Acknowledgements

I am a citizen of the world, known to all and to all a stranger.

Erasmus of Rotterdam

At the moment of my application I stated that, for me, participating in the Erasmus program is being part of Europe's history. The accomplishment of this dream of mine and the success of my internship would not be possible without the support of many people and institutions, to whom I here properly acknowledge and thank.

To Professor Helena Caria, I give my warmest thanks for all the support given before and during this internship, for always being in touch when I was away and for supporting my path during these 3 years of my bachelors degree. To Professor Vera van Noort, for the unique opportunity of being able to work in the CSB research group and being able to participate in the groundbreaking DARTpaths project. To Diksha Bhalla, to my colleagues at the CSB group and to the members of DARTpaths project for participating in the daily life of my Erasmus mobility.

To Professor Francisco Pina Martins, for being what I call 'bioinformatics in person', for being a mentor, for recognizing value in me and for supporting my endeavours all the way. To the past and present coordinators of the bioinformatics bachelors degree (Professors António Gonçalves, Gabriela Gomes, Helena Caria, Raquel Barreira, Vitor Barbosa and Sónia Santos) and all the other Professors I have met during this time of my life in Barreiro. To Professor Gabriela Gomes for putting up with me when I bothered about the Erasmus mobility, scholarships and other issues, and to Professor Marta Justino for teaching me subjects in a way so captivating that I have decided to keep studying in my masters and for motivating me into

giving this last push on my report. To the head of Escola Superior de Tecnologia do Barreiro do Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal, Professor Pedro Neto, for doing everything you can to elevate this school, that I can call home.

To the friends and colleagues that have shared these years with me and, in particular, to those who kept in touch and helped me during my stay abroad. To Diogo Almeida, my best friend. To João Pedro Bastos and Liliana Canguero for being my helping hands in Leuven.

Last but not least, I thank my brothers Inês, Pedro and Rita. You were and are my counselors and guidance, my support net, my family.

For the financial support, in the form of scholarships or monetary complements, I hereby proper thank the Agência Nacional Erasmus+, the Santander bank, and the Direção-Geral do Ensino Superior.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

3R - Reduce, Refine and Replace

AOP - Adverse Outcome Pathways

BASH - Bourne Again SHell

DART - Developmental and Reproduction Toxicity

DL - Duplication-Loss

DTL - Duplication-Transfer-Loss

ECHA - European Chemicals Agency

FDA - Food and Drug Administration

FTP - File Transfer Protocol

GNU - GNU's Not Unix!

ICH - International Conference for Harmonization

REACH - Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals

TSV - Tab Separated Values

Resumo

Os testes à toxicidade no desenvolvimento e reprodução (DART) requerem a utilização de um grande número de mamíferos (ratos e coelhos), e traduzem-se em custos elevados para a indústria. Sistemas de testagem alternativa em animais - como os das amibas, nemátodes e embriões de peixe-zebra - são utilizados com o objetivo de reduzir o número de mamíferos testados. Não existe atualmente nenhuma abordagem sistemática global (que permita *data mining* ou *querying* de perguntas "e se ...?") que permita avaliar a relevância da espécie, a utilidade e o domínio de aplicabilidade dos modelos disponíveis (modelos convencionais *in vivo* de mamíferos e sistemas alternativos não-mamíferos) de avaliação de DART.

Uma relação forte, entre dados de genes específicos e respostas fenotípicas específicas entre organismos, é essencial para o desenvolvimento de sistemas alternativos fiáveis de testagem DART em não-mamíferos, bem como para a definição dos domínios de aplicabilidade destes modelos.

Neste projeto, foi introduzido um novo organismo modelo numa ferramenta que permite estabelecer relações entre fenótipos DART e vias metabólicas moleculares subjacentes. Foi automatizado um processo de download e atualização de ficheiros de dados e foi criado um código para extração de genes ortólogos de ficheiros não-processados.

DART; 3Rs; fenótipos; automação; ortólogos; alternativas

Abstract

Testing for developmental and reproduction toxicity (DART) hazard requires the use of large numbers of mammals (rats and rabbits), and leads to high costs for industry. Alternative test systems like amoeba's, nematodes and zebrafish embryo's are used with the aim to reduce the number of mammalian test animals. There is currently no overall systematic approach (to enable data mining or query 'what if' questions) to assess the species relevance, usefulness and applicability domain of the available model systems (conventional in vivo mammalian animal models and alternative non-mammalian systems) used to assess DART. Reliably linking data of specific genes with specific responses between organisms is essential to the development of reliable alternative non-mammalian DART test systems, as well as defining the applicability domains of these models.

In this project, a new model organism was introduced in a tool that establishes relationships between DART phenotypes and underlying molecular metabolic pathways. A process of downloading and updating data files was automated and a script was created for extracting orthologous genes from unprocessed files.

DART; 3Rs; phenotypes; automation; orthologues; alternative

1 Introduction

This internship was integrated into the DARTpaths project, whose aim is to develop a platform that provides a holistic approach to DART alternative testing. With this application, researchers will be able to search chemical compounds, select pathways of interest, and discover conserved orthologs between various model organisms. The ultimate goal is to provide as much existing information as possible to researchers in order to Reduce and Refine their testing and (when possible) to Replace their model organisms for non-mammalian subjects.

1.1 Goals of the Internship

The general goal of the Internship Curricular Unit is to consolidate the learning process carried by the student over the 3 years of the Bachelor's degree and to develop new grounds of knowledge in the Bioinformatics area.

Besides those general goals, these project-specific goals were also defined:

- To mine biological data, specifically orthology to improve Python programming regarding mutant-phenotype and toxicity data;
- To develop and implement novel methods for data representation;
- To understand the societal impact of data analysis and integration on Replacement, Refinement and Reduction of animal testing.

1.2 Characterization of the Hosting Institution

The internship was developed at the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KU Leuven), in Belgium. One of Europe's oldest universities, KU Leuven has

been ranked in the last four years as Europe's most innovative university and currently ranks 45th at the Times Higher Education's World University Rankings 2021.

Integrated at KU Leuven's Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, the Department of Microbial and Molecular Systems (M²S) is home to the Centre of Microbial and Plant Genetics (CMPG), who hosts the Computational Systems Biology research group, where this internship's work was carried out. This research group is coordinated by Professor Vera van Noort, was established in 2013 and uses computational biology tools to interpret publicly available data as well as data from collaborators. The graphical identities of these institutions are available on Figure 1

Figure 1: Graphical identities of CMPG (left) and KU Leuven (right)

1.3 Internship schedule and Developed tasks

During the progress of the internship, with the project goals in mind, the following tasks were given:

- **Task A** - Research and familiarization with the existing materials;
- **Task B** - Insertion of *Drosophila melanogaster* as a new model organism;
- **Task C** - Automation of the download/update of data files;

- **Task D** - Orthologous genes extraction from Notung files + Summarization of results;
- **Task E** - Participation in Lab meetings/Journal Club (CSB group + DARTpaths project meetings);
- **Task F** - Writing of the Internship Report.

The execution of these tasks was completed in the timeframes stated in Figure 2. The period of execution of this internship occurred between February and July of 2021.

Due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic and the travel restrictions associated to it, this internship was started in Portugal (in telework) and completed in Belgium (present at the Lab and in telework).

Figure 2: Internship schedule by tasks

For reasons of future publication in scientific journals of the work developed and reasons of intellectual property of the partner companies in this project, only parts of the code, written from scratch or altered during this internship, are made available. In case of need of access to the entirety of the code, please contact the author of this report and his supervisor.

2 State of the Art / Fundamental Theory

There is no doubt that animal testing has contributed immensely to scientific progress and to the enhancement of quality of life to Humans with the development of new medicines and treatments [1]. With this purpose, international regulations and legislation as REACH, in the European Union, impose mandatory animal testing on chemical products to determine their safety for human consumption or use [2]. However, the conventional types of animal testing raise ethical questions such as 'Why should the use of animals in research be acceptable in cases where it would be unacceptable to use humans?' or 'Can any use of animals by humans be justified?' [3].

Therefore, the scientific community has been struggling with the dilemma: How to maintain animal welfare and respect ethical guidelines while needing to perform mandatory-by-law tests in animals?

The application of the 3R principles and new alternative testing methods provide some answers.

2.1 Biological Background

2.1.1 Developmental and Reproduction Toxicity (DART)

DART is a field of study in toxicology where the interference of chemical substances or medicines in normal reproduction or development is assessed. This includes adverse effects on sexual function and fertility in adult males and females, as well as developmental toxicity in the offspring [4]. According to the International Conference for Harmonization (ICH; 2015) guideline for the "Detection of toxicity to reproduction for medicinal products", DART testing entails the following study types [5]:

- ICH 4.1.1. - Fertility and early embryonic development to implantation;

- ICH 4.1.2. Pre- and postnatal development, including maternal function;
- ICH 4.1.3.–Embryo-fetal development.

With the motto "no data, no market" in mind, regulatory agencies like the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) require DART testing on new substances and chemicals via legislation (ie. REACH legislation in Europe) [2] [5].

2.1.2 The 3R Principles for Ethical Testing and Alternative Testing Methods

The 3R Principles were introduced by Russel and Burch (1959) to provide a framework for performing more humane animal research [6] [7]. The following scheme briefly defines the 3Rs:

	Standard	Contemporary
Replacement	Methods which avoid or replace the use of animals	Accelerating the development and use of models and tools, based on the latest science and technologies, to address important scientific questions without the use of animals
Reduction	Methods which minimise the number of animals used per experiment	Appropriately designed and analysed animal experiments that are robust and reproducible, and truly add to the knowledge base
Refinement	Methods which minimise animal suffering and improve welfare	Advancing animal welfare by exploiting the latest <i>in vivo</i> technologies and by improving understanding of the impact of welfare on scientific outcomes

Figure 3: Scheme summarizing the 3R Principles [6]

As a consequence of the 3R principles, conventional methods for animal testing eventually became considered less and less appropriate. These methods also present efficiency disadvantages by being time-consuming and expensive [8]. Alternative methods for testing became popular due to the advantages comparing to conventional testing [9]:

- are 3Rs compliant;
- uses computational resources;
- based on predictive studies (existing literature);
- resorts to non-mammalian model organisms.

2.1.3 Adverse Outcome Pathways, Orthology and Model Organisms (*Drosophila melanogaster*)

A new alternative method for DART testing is the inference of orthologous relations between human and non-human genes that are key in Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP).

The AOP concept provides insights to the sequence of molecular events initiated from the interaction with toxic compounds, until an adverse effect is observed as outcome. This approach helps focus on identifying the molecular pathways involved in toxicological events [10].

Regarding orthology, two genes of different species are orthologous when they have descended from a common ancestor. Orthologous genes tend to be similar in molecular and biological functions to each other. This gives insight to the relationships between species, in here between humans and the focused model organisms [11].

Drosophila melanogaster, known colloquially as the fruit fly, is an ovipositor fly that feeds primarily on unripe or ripe fruits [12]. Over the past five decades, *Drosophila* has become a predominant model used to understand how genes direct the development of an embryo from a single cell to a mature multicellular organism [13]. From a genomics perspective, the genome of *Drosophila* is 60% homologous to that of humans, less redundant, and about 75% of the genes responsible for human diseases have homologs in flies [14].

The logic behind this new alternative testing method is the following:

1. A non-human subject is exposed to a chemical substance that induces a DART adverse outcome;
2. The pathway that was triggered is identified, and so are the key genes of that pathway;

3. Using phylogenetic tools, orthologous relationships are mapped between human genes and the subject's genes that interfered with the pathway;
 - If the genes are not orthologous - the identified key genes will most likely not be present in the human pathway and an adverse outcome may not be triggered in humans [11].
 - If the genes are orthologous - those identified key genes are enriched with phenotypic information, from databases and pre-existing literature, and conclusions can be drawn about the possible adverse outcomes that the chemical substance may induce in humans [11].

2.2 Computational Background

2.2.1 Python

Python is a widely used general-purpose and high level programming language. It was mainly developed for emphasis on code readability, and its syntax allows programmers to express concepts in fewer lines of code [15].

2.2.2 Git

Git is a free and open source distributed version control system designed to handle everything from small to very large projects with speed and efficiency [16].

2.2.3 Bash

Bash is the GNU Project's shell—the Bourne Again SHell. This is an sh-compatible shell that incorporates useful features from the Korn shell (ksh) and the C shell (csh). It is intended to conform to the IEEE POSIX

P1003.2/ISO 9945.2 Shell and Tools standard. It offers functional improvements over sh for both programming and interactive use. In addition, most sh scripts can be run by Bash without modification [17].

2.2.4 Notung

Notung a gene tree-species tree reconciliation software package that supports duplication-loss (DL) and duplication-transfer-loss (DTL) event models with a parsimony-based optimization criterion. This software utilizes novel, efficient algorithms for reconstructing the history of gene duplications and losses, for rooting gene trees based on duplication/loss parsimony and for the rearrangement of weakly supported areas of gene trees [18] [19].

3 Materials and Methods

As the work developed in this internship results from the continuation of the work carried out within the scope of a master's thesis of another student, my main raw material was the phenotype enrichment tool created by that student. That tool consists of a Python script that maps orthologous genes in pathways and statistically examines whether phenotypes are enriched or not by comparing the outcome to control or reference background, returning the enriched phenotypes caused by toxicological events as a result.

Only *Caenorhabditis elegans* (a nematode), *Danio rerio* (zebrafish), *Dictyostelium discoideum* (a slime mould) and *Mus musculus* (house mouse) were used as model organisms in the initial version of the tool.

The steps performed by the phenotype enrichment tool are summarized in the following points:

1. Calling of the tool (Python file) via terminal or within an automated pipeline with command line arguments (pathway name and ID, and path to data files folder);
2. Reading of the data files as dataframes in the python environment and selection of the columns of interest in each dataframe;
3. Mapping: pathway to human genes, human genes to orthologous genes, orthologous genes to phenotypes;
4. Execution the enrichment analysis;
5. Output of the results into datafiles and closing of the tool.

The input data was obtained from the species' specific data sources stated in Appendix I. Figure 4 outlines the inputs and outputs of this phenotype enrichment tool.

Figure 4: Inputs and Outputs of the Phenotype Enrichment Tool

3.1 Insertion of *Drosophila melanogaster* as a new model organism

For the task of adding *Drosophila melanogaster* to this tool, the FlyBase database was selected to obtain data on alleles and phenotypes for this species. As in the case of slime mold, there was no need to resort to another database to obtain ontologies of the phenotypes.

The main change done to the original python script of the tool was the addition of snippets of code for the the data reading and mapping steps (see points 2 and 3 above) for *D. melanogaster*. As the code structure was similar between species, some reuse of code was made to guarantee coherence between versions.

3.2 Automation of the download/update of data files

In the original version of the phenotype enrichment tool, there was a need for the manual download of data files by the user from user-oriented data marts, FTP sites and species specific databases. This methodology is problematic because of the following reasons:

- Laborious method for the user or system administrator;
- Information gets quickly outdated;
- Not recommended procedure for an automated pipeline.

The solution for this was the automation of the process of download and update of data files using Python libraries. The changes in the code of the enrichment tool had to be tailor-made to the different data sources, since there was no universal approach that could be used due to the diversity of formats used by the databases to store their information. A description of the purpose of each library used is stated in the following points:

- `os` - used for deleting older files;
- `datetime` - used to compare the time of creation of the data files with the time when the instance of the tool started to being executed;
- `pathlib` - file path management;

- `wget`, `urllib3` - download of data files;
- `gzip` - unzip (when necessary) of data files.

A timeframe of 24 hours was set as a maximum period between the last update of data files and the execution of the tool. After that period, the functions for download of the data files and deletion of older ones are activated when running a new tool instance and a new 24 hours period starts.

3.3 Orthologous genes extraction from Notung files + Summarization of results

Within the goal of the DARTpaths project of summarizing biological data for easy access and visualization by researchers, there was the need of adding orthology data of *Drosophila melanogaster* to the already existing data of other non-human species used as model organisms in this platform. The Notung software was used, by a colleague, to perform phylogenetic inference and extracting, in consequence, orthologous matches between human and non-human genes.

Due to the long period of computation involved, the task of extracting human orthologs of *D. melanogaster* was never included in the batch of tasks for Notung to execute (unlike the case of the preexisting model organisms). As the output of the execution of Notung included data on orthologous relations between human genes and genes from all non-human species in a raw format, this constituted the basis for the task of extracting orthologous genes of *D. melanogaster* through a bioinformatical approach.

A Python script was written for this, with the following workflow:

1. Calling of the script, reading of files with a specific name structure (see figure 5), and verification of the existence of a matrix with species in the columns and in the rows;

2. Dropping of empty values and filtering of species to only show the human orthologs of *D. melanogaster*;
3. Addition of the resulting data (orthologs) to a TSV (Tab Separated Values) file, summarizing all the results.
4. Repetition of the process for each file and closing of the script.

Figure 5: Inputs and Outputs of the Notung Ortholog Extractor

4 Results and Discussion

Introducing *Drosophila* as a new model organism into the phenotype enrichment tool enables further analysis on DART. This implied the addition of 33 lines of code and the change of 1 line that already existed. The addition of lines was mainly focused on the orthologous gene mapping step of this tool, as the other steps had an universal approach to all model organisms.

Due to the data organization defined by FlyBase, the matching of genes with phenotypes had alleles as an intermediary step. In other words, there was a need of using python resources to connect genes to alleles and alleles to phenotypes, instead of just connecting directly genes to phenotypes. This had previously occurred with data of slime mould, so the solution for the data connection with *Drosophila* was replicated from the solution designed by the Masters student for slime mould.

The reuse of code from other model organisms enabled the assurance of coherence and continuity of the script structure of this tool, translating into efficiency. Figure 6 shows an example of the differences between the original version of the phenotype enrichment tool and the version that now includes *D. melanogaster*.

```
elif organism == "mouse":
    df_mouse = pd.read_csv(Mouse_ENSEMBL_orthology_database, delimiter='\t',
header = 'infer')
    selectgenes= df_mouse[['Mouse gene name','Gene stable ID']].copy()

elif organism == "slimemould":
    df_slime = pd.read_csv(Slime_mould_ENSEMBL_orthology_database, delimiter='\t',
header='infer')
    selectgenes= df_slime[['homology_gene_stable_id','gene_stable_id ']].copy()
```

```
elif organism == "mouse":
    df_mouse = pd.read_csv(Mouse_ENSEMBL_orthology_database, delimiter='\t', header =
'infer')
    selectgenes= df_mouse[['Mouse gene name','Gene stable ID']].copy()

elif organism == "slimemould":
    df_slime = pd.read_csv(Slime_mould_ENSEMBL_orthology_database, delimiter='\t',
header='infer')
    selectgenes= df_slime[['homology_gene_stable_id','gene_stable_id ']].copy()
```

```
+ elif organism == "dmelanogaster":
+     df_dmelanogaster = pd.read_csv(Fly_ENSEMBL_orthology_database,delimiter='\t',
+header='infer')
+     selectgenes = df_dmelanogaster[['Drosophila melanogaster gene stable ID', 'Gene
+stable ID']].dropna().copy()
+
+
```

Figure 6: Example of the differences between the original version (top image) and the current version (bottom image) of the phenotype enrichment tool, now including *D. melanogaster*

Due to a confusion in the file storage strategy of the project's Git repository, the file I was initially working on was an old version that only did the enrichment analysis of the species indicated by the user. As soon as this issue was clarified, the necessary changes were introduced in the most current version of the tool, which performs the analysis of all species simultaneously without the need for the user to indicate any species.

For downloading and updating the data files that feed the phenotype enrichment tool, 389 lines of codes were added and 15 lines of code were deleted. During the execution of the tool, when these lines were activated, the download and update task took 5 minutes to be completed, in average. This represents a big difference when comparing with the previous version, where the process of only reading the data files just took seconds. But, in the previous version, the task of downloading the data files had to be executed manually which translated in more time dedicated by the user to a task in a non-automated fashion.

Despite following the same structure, the snippet of code for each specie was different due to the variety of databases and specificity of formats in the stored data. In example, some data files from FlyBase were download in a compressed format with gzip and extra lines of code were needed to decompress those files. This is the reason why the lines of code for download were not inserted in one defined function that could call that process, but it is something to explore in further work.

The data files that resulted of this download process were stored in the TSV format and shared a similar, if not identical, structure that uniformizes and eases data visualization for the bioinformatician (but not the end-user), when analyzing those files.

An example of the code for downloading and updating the data files for *D. melanogaster* is shown in Appendix II.

Extracting orthologous genes from Notung files required the writing of a Python script from scratch. Some disadvantages of this script are the need of being located in the same folder as the data files and the fact that it is not structured in functions.

Proof of concept was made with data on *Drosophila sp*, and is now ready to be extended to other species. This tool can be used, not only in the context of this project, but for other purposes as well.

The code of this Notung Ortholog Extractor is available on Appendix III.

The weekly monitoring, whether in lab group, project and advisor meetings, was essential for the outcomes of this internship and for the writing of this report.

5 Conclusions

The work carried out in the internship allowed to expand the degree of DART analysis on non-human species and brought an improvement in the methods, with the automation of data availability, in the DARTpaths project. This is an ambitious project that could leverage the revolution of the alternative methods for animal testing and I am proud to give a positive evaluation of my participation in this project.

The general goal of the Internship Curricular Unit was successfully achieved and the project specific goals were fulfilled, although more emphasis was placed on some goals than others:

- **To mine biological data, specifically orthology to improve Python programming regarding mutant-phenotype and toxicity data** - *Drosophila melanogaster*, one of the most important model organisms in toxicology, was included in the DARTpaths platform through the phenotype enrichment tool;
- **To develop and implement novel methods for data representation** - a method for extracting and summarizing data of orthologous genes from Notung files was created and tested with the *Drosophila sp* and extrapolable to other species;
- **To understand the societal impact of data analysis and integration on Replacement, Refinement and Reduction of animal testing** - the research of the State of the Art and the weekly meetings provided more context and in-depth specialization on the ethical testing issues.

It was also possible to deepen the subjects learned in the curricular units of Biological Sequence Analysis, Molecular and Cell Biology, Data Mining

and Structural and Evolutionary Genomics.

The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic had an impact during this curricular internship due to telework and travel restrictions, but it is possible to make a very positive assessment of the reality of the period in mobility compared to the initial expectations.

From the perspective of my professional future, this project allowed me to open up horizons, explore the field of Evolutionary and Developmental Biology and decide to enter a master's degree in this area. The Bioinformatics area will always accompany my professional path and allow me to be at the forefront of scientific research in Biology.

6 Conclusões

O trabalho desenvolvido estágio permitiu expandir o grau de análise DART em espécies não-humanas e trouxe uma melhoria nos métodos, com a automatização da disponibilização de dados no projeto DARTpaths. Este é um projeto ambicioso que poderá potenciar a revolução nos métodos de testagem alternativa em animais e é com orgulho que faço uma avaliação positiva da minha participação neste projeto.

O objetivo geral da Unidade Curricular de Estágio foi alcançado com sucesso e os objetivos específicos do projeto foram cumpridos, embora tenha sido dada mais ênfase a alguns que a outros:

- **Extraír dados biológicos, especificamente dados de genes ortólogos para melhorar a programação em Python em relação a fenótipos mutantes e dados de toxicidade** - *Drosophila melanogaster*, um dos organismos modelo mais importantes em toxicologia, foi incluída na plataforma DARTpaths através da ferramenta de enriquecimento de fenótipos;
- **Desenvolver e implementar novos métodos para representação de dados** - foi criado um método para extrair e resumir dados de genes ortólogos de ficheiros Notung, testado com a espécie *Drosophila* e extrapolável a outras espécies;
- **Compreender o impacto social da análise e integração de dados na Substituição, Refinamento e Redução de testes em animais** - a pesquisa do estado da arte e os encontros semanais forneceram mais contexto e especialização com profundidade nas questões da testagem ética.

Em particular, foi possível aprofundar matérias aprendidas nas unidades curriculares de Análise de Sequências Biológicas, Biologia Molecular e

Celular, Data Mining e Genómica Estrutural e Evolutiva.

A pandemia de SARS-CoV-2 teve impacto no decorrer deste estágio curricular por força do tele-trabalho e das restrições de viagem, mas é possível fazer uma apreciação muito positiva da realidade do período em mobilidade em comparação com as expetativas iniciais.

Na perspetiva de um futuro profissional, este projeto permitiu-me abrir horizontes, explorar o ramo da Biologia Evolutiva e do Desenvolvimento e decidir ingressar num mestrado nessa área. A área da Bioinformática irá sempre acompanhar o meu percurso profissional e permitir-me estar na vanguarda da investigação científica em Biologia.

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A Appendices

A.1 Appendix I - List of species specific data sources used in the Phenotype Enrichment Tool

Type	Species	Database
Pathway	<i>Homo Sapiens</i>	Reactome
Orthologs	<i>C. elegans</i>	ENSEMBL
	<i>D. rerio</i>	
	<i>M. musculus</i>	
	<i>D. discoideum</i>	
	<i>D. melanogaster</i>	
Phenotype (Genotype Association)	<i>C. elegans</i>	WormBase
	<i>D. rerio</i>	ZFIN
	<i>M. musculus</i>	MousePhenotypes
	<i>D. discoideum</i>	DictyBase
	<i>D. melanogaster</i>	FlyBase
	<i>C. elegans</i>	WormBase
Phenotype Term (Ontology)	<i>D. rerio</i>	ZFIN
	<i>D. rerio</i>	GO
	<i>M. musculus</i>	MPO

A.2 Appendix II - Example of the code for downloading and updating the data files for *D. melanogaster*

```
1
2 elif organism == "dmelanogaster":
3     ### ENSEMBL DATABASES (orthologs) ##### same as the one
4     used for orthology mapping part
5     Fly_ENSEMBL_orthology_database =
6     path_to_orthologs_database_folder+"/"+
7     Orthology_human_dmelanogaster_ensembl101_unique.txt"
8     path = path_to_orthologs_database_folder
9     xml_query = ""<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
10    <!DOCTYPE Query>
11    <Query virtualSchemaName = "default" formatter = "TSV"
12    header = "1" uniqueRows = "1" count = ""
13    datasetConfigVersion = "0.6" >
14
15    <Dataset name = "hsapiens_gene_ensembl" interface = "
16    default" >
17    <Attribute name = "ensembl_gene_id" />
18    <Attribute name = "ensembl_gene_id_version" />
19    <Attribute name = "
20    dmelanogaster_homolog_associated_gene_name" />
21    <Attribute name = "dmelanogaster_homolog_ensembl_gene
22    " />
23    <Attribute name = "
24    dmelanogaster_homolog_orthology_type" />
25    </Dataset>
26    </Query>""
27    my_file = Path(Fly_ENSEMBL_orthology_database)
28    if my_file.exists():
29        filetime = datetime.fromtimestamp(os.path.getctime(
30        Fly_ENSEMBL_orthology_database))
31        if filetime < days_pass:
32            os.remove(Fly_ENSEMBL_orthology_database)
33        r = http.request('GET', 'http://www.ensembl.org/
```

```

biomart/martservice?query='+xml_query)
24     outfile = open(Fly_ENSEMBL_orthology_database, 'w
')
25     outfile.write(r.data.decode("utf-8"))
26     outfile.close()
27     else:
28     r = http.request('GET', 'http://www.ensembl.org/biomart
/martservice?query='+xml_query)
29     outfile = open(Fly_ENSEMBL_orthology_database, 'w')
30     outfile.write(r.data.decode("utf-8"))
31     outfile.close()
32     ### Phenotype database
33     path = path_to_phenotype_database_folder
34     Fly_gene_to_allele_database =
path_to_phenotype_database_folder+"/"+"
Fly_fbal_to_fbgn_fb_current_release.tsv"
35     Fly_allele_to_phenotype_database =
path_to_phenotype_database_folder+"/"+"
Fly_allele_phenotypic_data_fb_current_release.tsv"
36     my_file = Path(Fly_gene_to_allele_database)
37     if my_file.exists():
38         filetime = datetime.fromtimestamp(os.path.getctime(
Fly_gene_to_allele_database))
39         if filetime < days_pass:
40             os.remove(Fly_gene_to_allele_database)
41             wget.download('http://ftp.flybase.org/releases/
current/precomputed_files/alleles/
fbal_to_fbgn_fb_FB2021_02.tsv.gz', out=
Fly_gene_to_allele_database)
42     else:
43         wget.download('http://ftp.flybase.org/releases/current/
precomputed_files/alleles/fbal_to_fbgn_fb_FB2021_02.tsv.gz
', out=Fly_gene_to_allele_database)
44
45     my_file = Path(Fly_allele_to_phenotype_database)
46     if my_file.exists():
47         filetime = datetime.fromtimestamp(os.path.getctime(

```

```
Fly_allele_to_phenotype_database))
48     if filetime < days_pass:
49         os.remove(Fly_allele_to_phenotype_database)
50         wget.download('http://ftp.flybase.org/releases/
current/precomputed_files/alleles/
allele_phenotypic_data_fb_2021_02.tsv.gz', out=
Fly_allele_to_phenotype_database)
51     else:
52         wget.download('http://ftp.flybase.org/releases/current/
precomputed_files/alleles/
allele_phenotypic_data_fb_2021_02.tsv.gz', out=
Fly_allele_to_phenotype_database)
```

A.3 Appendix III - Code of the Notung Ortholog Extractor

```
1
2 ### This tool extracts D.Melanogaster orthologs from Human
   genes
3 ### by searching each Notung file, then placing the orthologs
   in a dataframe and finally by appending that that to a
   TSV file.
4 ### If a TSV file already exists, it will be eliminated when
   running this script.
5
6 #Library installation
7 import pandas as pd
8 import os
9 from pathlib import Path
10
11 #States the path where the script is stored
12 path = os.path.abspath(os.path.dirname("__file__"))
13 print(path)
14 #Function for crawling the folders, loading the Notung file
   data to a dataframe, filter its content to only store the
   intended information (Drosophila and Human),
15 #transform the data to the intended form for output, and
   finally send the dataframe to the TSV file. This process
   occurs for each Notung file and the outputs are appended
16 #to the same TSV file.
17
18 my_file = Path("Notung_DMelanogaster_orthologs.txt")
19 if my_file.exists():
20     os.remove("Notung_DMelanogaster_orthologs.txt")
21 for root, dirs, files in os.walk(path):
22     for name in files:
23         #print(files)
24         if name.endswith("ReadyForNotung.nw.gtpruned.rooting
   .0.rearrange.0.homologs.txt"):
25             filename = os.path.abspath(os.path.join(root,
   name))
```

```

26     print(filename)
27     lines = open(filename).readlines()
28     strToFind = "DrosophilaMelanosgaster"
29     count = len(open(filename).readlines( ))
30     if count > 10:
31         ortho_data = pd.read_csv(filename, delimiter=
'\t', sep="\t", header = 12, index_col=0)
32
33         Dmelanogaster_cols = [col for col in
ortho_data.columns if 'DrosophilaMelanogaster' in col]
34         ortho_data = ortho_data[Dmelanogaster_cols]
35         ortho_data = ortho_data[(ortho_data == '0')]
36         ortho_data = ortho_data.dropna(how="all")
37         ortho_data = ortho_data.replace("0", pd.
Series(ortho_data.columns, ortho_data.columns))
38         ortho_data[Dmelanogaster_cols] = ortho_data[
Dmelanogaster_cols].replace({'7227.':''}, regex=True)
39         ortho_data[Dmelanogaster_cols] = ortho_data[
Dmelanogaster_cols].replace({'__DrosophilaMelanogaster':''}
}, regex=True)
40         ortho_data.columns = range(ortho_data.shape
[1])
41         ortho_data = ortho_data.transpose()
42
43         hSapiens_cols = [col for col in ortho_data.
columns if 'HomoS' in col]
44         ortho_data = ortho_data[hSapiens_cols]
45         ortho_data.columns = ortho_data.columns.str.
replace(r"9606.", "")
46         ortho_data.columns = ortho_data.columns.str.
replace(r "__HomoSapiens", "")
47         ortho_data = ortho_data.dropna(how="all")
48
49         ortho_data = ortho_data.transpose()
50         ortho_data
51         print(ortho_data)
52         ortho_data.to_csv("

```

```
Notung_DMelanogaster_orthologs.txt", header=False, mode='a', sep = "\t")
```